

THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES THAT HAVE IMPLEMENTED A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

BADALOV NOMOZ JURABOYEVICH

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, associate professor,
Phone number: +998903110662; nomozbadalov@gmail.com

RUSTAMOV NASIM TULEGENOVICH

associate professor - International Kazakh-Turkish University

Annotation: *It is necessary to inform all the employees of the organization about the importance of fulfilling the requirements of consumers and the requirements of laws and regulations, to determine the organization's policies and goals in the field of quality, to conduct an analysis by the management, to prove their commitment to the development, implementation and continuous improvement of the quality management system. It is important to provide and provide available resources.*

Key words: *Quality management, management system, quality management, audit, internal audit, external audit, periodicity of analysis, resource, competition, process, system.*

The top management of the organization should inform all employees of the organization about the importance of the development, implementation and continuous improvement of the quality management system, the requirements of consumers, as well as the fulfillment of the requirements of laws and regulations, the determination of the organization's policies and goals in the field of quality, and the management's analysis , it is important to provide and provide the necessary resources.

The obligations of the management should be specified in the quality policy signed by the head of the enterprise, in the documents defining the goals in the quality field, in the quality manual, in the documents showing the results of the analysis of the quality management system by the top management. The responsibilities of the management are confirmed by the creation and operation of

the quality management system, the allocation of necessary resources to achieve the efficiency and effectiveness of the processes [1].

Adapting to customer requirements, the management of the organization must ensure that their requirements are identified and fulfilled in order to increase customer satisfaction. The organization depends on its customers, so it must understand their current needs, fulfill their requirements and strive to satisfy their needs. The management should ensure that the activities of the organization are aimed at satisfying the demands, needs and desires of consumers.

In the process of marketing activities, the management must organize activities to fulfill consumer requirements, taking into account the research of consumer requirements, requests and needs, determining consumer requirements when signing contracts for product supply, and taking into account consumer requirements when forming project input data during product design and development. The organization must have a system for collecting, studying and analyzing data from all sources that provide evidence about the level of customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction criteria and evaluation methods should be developed. This information should be used in developing organizational goals and planning product quality [2].

Policy in the field of quality. The top management of the organization should include the commitment to the quality policy, compliance with the organization's goals, satisfaction of the requirements and continuous improvement of the quality management system, setting the goals in the quality area and creating a basis for analysis, communicated to the employees of the organization and being understandable to them, its suitability is always must ensure that it is analyzed in order to maintain it.

One of the main tasks of quality management is to define the goals that the organization is working to achieve and developing [3].

For example, increasing product sales is a goal for the marketing department.

The goals should be clear not only to the employees of the organization, but also to other interested parties.

Objectives for lower levels of management should be defined in the form of specific tasks that must be completed by specific employees in specific departments within specified time periods [4].

In the development of quality policy, top management must take into account the potential for future improvements necessary for the success of the organization, the planned level of customer satisfaction, the opportunities for professional growth of the organization's employees, the needs and desires of all interested parties, the necessary resources, the contribution of suppliers and partners. Continuous quality assurance of products and services should be the main focus of the organization's quality policy. The quality policy must be signed by the head of the enterprise. Management must ensure that the policy is understood, implemented and supported at all levels. It is important to communicate the documented quality policy to all employees of the enterprise.

Objectives in planning and quality. Top management must ensure that quality objectives, and therefore those necessary to meet product requirements, are set in the appropriate departments of the organization and at the required level. Quality objectives should be measurable and aligned with the quality policy. On the basis of the adopted quality policy, the top management of the organization should develop clear goals and ensure the management of activities to achieve the goals that lead to the improvement of the organization's performance [5].

In developing the organization's goals, the top management should consider the organization's current and future needs and consumer desires, relevant information on the results of the organization's management, quality indicators of products and processes, the level of satisfaction of all interested parties, the results of self-assessment of the organization's activities, the results of the assessment of competitors, control to evaluate the activity it is necessary to take into account the determination of points, the possibilities of improving products, processes, management system, and the necessary resources to achieve the goals set ahead.

In order for the organization to achieve its stated goals, top management must ensure that quality goals are set for departments and at appropriate levels that are

aligned with the organization's goals. Responsibilities must be clearly defined for the achievement of set goals. Organizational goals must be measurable. This means that they are characterized by either specific values or projected performance that is not represented by a numerical value. Objectives in the field of quality are organizational quality programs, quality improvement activities, or other program documents traditionally developed by the organization, which include quality improvement, technical restructuring of the enterprise, introduction of advanced technologies, improvement of staff skills, improvement of interaction with suppliers, satisfaction of consumer requirements. can be specified in the form [6].

Quality management system planning. Management must plan the quality management system to achieve quality objectives, and ensure that the integrity of the quality management system is maintained when planning and making changes to it. The management should plan work on the creation of the enterprise quality management system in accordance with the requirements of the international standards of the ISO 9000 series for the enterprise quality management system. When analyzing the quality management system, the management should take into account the changes in the structural structure, organization, and processes, and make decisions on the evaluation of the effectiveness of the quality system. Decisions made on the development of the quality management system, the implementation of changes in the current system, must guarantee the integrity of the quality management system by eliminating contradictions with the goals and objectives of the organization [7].

Responsibility, authority and information sharing. Responsibilities and powers Management should ensure that responsibilities and powers are defined and communicated to the organization's employees. The responsibilities and authorities necessary to achieve the defined quality objectives should be defined by top management and communicated to all employees, and the procedure for employee interaction should be established when the quality management system is in operation. Employees engaged in quality-affecting activities should be provided with responsibility and authority, taking into account the principle of involvement

of enterprise workers in the quality management system. Management must ensure that all stakeholders at each level of the organization are informed of their responsibilities and authority. Information about responsibilities and authorities must be communicated to employees in order to effectively and efficiently implement and maintain the quality management system.

Responsibilities, powers, and interaction between departments and responsible persons are defined in the structural structure of the organization, orders and orders of the top management, regulations on structural units, job instructions, quality manual, quality system documents, work performance instructions, and other documents of the organization. In the distribution of responsibility and authority, the order of responsibility distribution and transfer of responsibilities to the organization's employees should be provided for the achievement of the organization's goals in the field of quality [8].

Management representative. The top management of the organization must appoint a representative of the management from among the management of the organization, and this representative, regardless of other tasks assigned to him, must implement the development of the processes necessary for the quality management system and ensure that they are kept in working condition, and provide reports to the top management of the organization about the operation of the quality management system and the need to improve it. should be responsible and empowered to help ensure awareness of customer requirements at all levels of the organization.

In order for the quality management system to work efficiently and effectively, senior management must provide a representative of senior management and, regardless of other tasks assigned to him, give him the responsibility and relevant authority for the following: to ensure the development, implementation and maintenance of quality management system processes in accordance with the requirements of ISO 9001, providing reports to senior management on the operation of the quality management system, as well as the needs related to its improvement, informing the management of the organization about consumer satisfaction, helping to ensure the study and understanding of consumer requirements throughout the

organization, informing interested parties about consumer complaints and objections, quality management to communicate with external organizations on issues related to the system.

The representative of the top management has the authority to carry out the following activities: planning and coordination of work on the creation of the organization's quality management system, leading the activities to determine the processes to be included in the quality management system, their sequence and interrelationship, management, measurement, analysis and improvement of quality management processes to lead activities on quality, organize the development of quality manual, quality system documents and keep them up to date, provide interested parties with quality manual and other documents of quality system, organization of quality record management activities, organization of collection and analysis of information from consumers on product quality and their satisfaction, planning, conducting, and formalizing results of internal audits of the quality management system, internal audits of the quality management system, corrective and preventive measures on the quality of products and processes it is considered necessary to have the ability to prepare receiving operations, organize activities for measurement, analysis and improvement of processes, develop activities for product quality improvement and continuous improvement, communicate with external organizations on quality management issues [9].

Internal information exchange. The management should ensure the development of appropriate processes of information exchange in the organization, in this regard, processes for the effectiveness of the quality management system. It is necessary for the management to ensure the awareness of the employees about the issues of quality management systems, about the goals in the field of quality, about the ways of achieving the set goals and evaluating the effectiveness of their achievement.

The responsibility for providing the company's employees with relevant information is assigned to the representative of the management. Employees of the enterprise should be informed about the quality policy of the organization, the goals

of the organization in the field of quality, the goals of the activities they participate in, their responsibilities and powers, the importance of fulfilling consumer requirements, the effectiveness and efficiency of processes, product quality, and the effectiveness of the quality management system. The content of the data and the form of their delivery to the employees of the organization is determined by the representative of the top management [10].

Analysis by management. The management should regularly conduct an analysis of the organization's quality management system to ensure its continued suitability, uniformity and effectiveness. In such an analysis, it is necessary to evaluate the possibilities of improving the quality management system and the need to make changes, as well as the policies and goals in the field of quality. Analysis by management is considered one of the effective mechanisms of quality system improvement. The analysis of the quality system carried out by the management of the organization should include the assessment of the implementation of the policy in the field of quality and the achievement of goals, the assessment of the effectiveness and efficiency of the quality management system, and the assessment of the opportunities for improving the quality management system.

The frequency of analysis of the quality management system is determined by the management based on the characteristics of the manufactured products, changes in the market situation, the presence of quality problems in the enterprise, the time the quality system has been operating and other factors.

Periodicity of the analysis: it can be once a quarter, once every six months, but it should not be less than once a year.

In order for the analysis to be carried out effectively, it is necessary to develop an analysis procedure. To conduct the analysis, it is recommended to establish a sequence of preparation of initial data by enterprise units [11].

The duties and responsibilities of the departments of the enterprise participating in the analysis and providing information should be determined, the composition and form of presentation of input data on the analysis and proposals for improving the

product, process and quality management system should be established for these departments.

Input data for analysis. Input data for analysis by the management are the results of audits, customer feedback, process efficiency and product conformity, the status of preventive and corrective actions, the implementation of decisions made on the results of previous analyzes of the management system, changes that may affect the quality management system, improvements should include recommendations and information on.

The list of information that should be included in the analysis materials submitted to the management includes the implementation of the decisions made on the previous analysis, inspections, including quality system and external audits of the product, inspections by regulatory agencies, as well as the results of internal audits, the results of product evaluation by consumers, their wishes and needs. satisfaction, consumer suggestions for improving product quality, existence of objections and complaints, dynamics of non-conformities, analysis of their occurrence, measures taken to prevent possible inconsistencies, analysis of inconsistencies that may arise as a result of changes in legislation, market conditions, equipment wear and other factors, the effectiveness of corrective and preventive actions, the requirements established in accordance with the law in contracts and the mandatory requirements of regulatory documents, also, enterprise documents include information on product conformity, including evaluation of technological processes, information on the effectiveness and efficiency of the processes provided for in the quality system, information on the need to change and improve quality management systems [12].

Analysis results. The results of the management's analysis will include actions and decisions aimed at the following: improving the efficiency of the quality management system and its processes, improving the product in accordance with consumer requirements, and providing the necessary resources.

The results of the management analysis should include decisions on improving the quality management system and processes, identifying opportunities to improve

the organization's activities, and increasing the level of product quality in accordance with consumer requirements.

The analysis process should provide a system for monitoring the implementation of the decisions made by the management based on the results of the analysis and evaluating their effectiveness in the subsequent analysis of the quality management system.

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